

STATE OF HEPATOCYTE BIOMEMBRANES IN LIVER PATHOLOGY

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Abstract. *In addition to the four - electron reduction of O₂, processes leading to the formation of superoxide anions and hydrogen peroxides are also possible in biological systems. When exposed to superoxides and peroxides, more toxic hydroxyl radicals are formed. They are one of the most probable activators of lipid peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids of phospholipids (LPO) with the formation of alkyl radicals (R), which promotes the free radical oxidation of lipids. It occurs under the influence of various agents, which include CCl₄ and heliotrin. These agents penetrate the cells well, where they metabolize while forming trichloromethyl, chlorines and pyrroles, which enhance LPO.*

Keywords: *membrane, LPO, MDA, lipids, lipid bilayer, phospholipids, gangliosides, enzymes, vitamins, proteins.*

Introduction. Membranes implement their functions due to structural components: phospholipids, gangliosides, enzymes, vitamins, proteins, microelements. It is well known that the main factor determining the structural organization and functional state of membranes is the phospholipid composition. Each phospholipid included in the membranes has a certain vital function: by its presence determine the activity of membrane-bound enzymes; affect the permeability of membranes; bind and transport ions; participate in the conjugation of electron transport processes. ; enhance energy in the cell, etc. Gangliosides with their hydrophobic part (ceramide, sphingosine, fatty acid) are immersed in the phospholipid bilayer, and the extended oligosaccharide part is oriented to the intercellular space. Such an association of phospholipids, gangliosides, proteins, as well as enzymes and antioxidants affects the functional activity of each of them and the membrane function as a whole.

The aim of the work is to identify the effect of the hepatotropic poison heliotrin on the intensity of lipid peroxidation, phospholipid composition and the activity of the antioxidant enzyme - superoxide dismutase (SOD).

Research methods. Heliotrin hepatitis in rats was induced by intramuscular administration of heliotrin according to the method of Abdullaev A.Kh. The intensity of lipid peroxidation (LPO) was determined by the amount of malonic dialdehyde (MDA) according to the method of I.D. Stalnaya and T.G. Garishvili. Fractionation of phospholipids was carried out by thin-layer chromatography. The amount of phospholipids was determined by the content of inorganic phosphorus using the method of V.E. Vaskovsky. The activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) was determined using the method of Mirza, J. Fridovich. The activity of hepatospecific enzymes was determined in the serum and blood of experimental rats: alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) using Biotest.

Results. Heliotrin hepatitis in rats was induced by subcutaneous administration of heliotrin using the method of Abdullaev A.Kh. A 9-fold increase in the amount of MDA was found in liver

homogenates. A 49% decrease in the amount of total phospholipids was found against the background of a predominant decrease in the amount of neutral fractions: phosphatidylcholine (PC) and phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) by 73%. The levels of lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC), phosphatidylserine (PS), and phosphatidic acid (PA) tended to increase by 2.5-2.6 times. The PC/LPC ratio decreased by 33%. SOD activity, on the contrary, decreased by 40%. The activity of ALT and AST in the blood serum of experimental animals increased by 2.4-2.6 times.

Discussion: The process of lipid peroxidation is a widespread phenomenon occurring in each membrane structure. Biotransformation of heliotrin occurs in the liver, forming highly toxic pyrroles that interfere with cell metabolism, accelerating the formation of fatty acid radicals, enhancing the peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids. This was evidenced by an increase in the concentration of MDA - the final, toxic product of lipid peroxidation formed as a result of the rupture of polyunsaturated fatty acids of phospholipids under the action of free radicals and pathogenic pyrroles formed during the metabolism of heliotrin in the liver. A jump in MDA concentration is also a consequence of an increase in the activity of lysosomal phospholipases, mainly phospholipases A2. An increase in MDA concentration serves as a marker of the degree of endogenous intoxication. MDA binds to DNA components, disrupting the structure and functions of DNA. MDA reduces the activity of Krebs cycle enzymes, catalase activity, glutathione peroxides. As a result, protein synthesis is disrupted, as well as enzymes of phospholipid biosynthesis.

Thus, an increase in the intensity of LPO, an increase in the activation of lysosomal enzymes, a disruption in the activity of enzymes of phospholipid biosynthesis leads to a decrease in the amount of total phospholipids against the background of a decrease in the amount of phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylethanolamine, cardiolipin and an increase in the amount of lysophosphatidylcholine, phosphatidic acid. Lysophosphatidylcholine is a product formed by the cleavage of unsaturated fatty acid from phosphatidylcholine under the influence of active phospholipase A2. As a result, the level of PC decreased and LPC increased. As a result, the PC / LPC ratio decreased by 33%. Phosphatidic acid is an intermediate substance in the synthesis of phospholipids. The accumulation of FA indicates the inhibition of phospholipid synthesis. Each phospholipid that is part of the membranes has a certain vital function: by its presence it determines the activity of membrane-bound enzymes; affects the permeability of membranes; binds and transports ions; participates in conjugation electron transport processes; enhance energy in the cell.

It is known that membrane lipids deserve attention by participating in the regulation of the hormonal effect. Regulation of the effect of hormones through the adenylate cyclase system is associated with the presence of PI and PS in the membrane. These phospholipids regulate the sensitivity of cyclase to adrenaline, glucagon, and thyroid hormones. The activities of Na⁺, K⁺-ATPase, Mg²⁺ + -ATPase depend on membrane lipids. It is assumed that the active centers of these enzymes are located mainly on the plasma membrane, and phospholipids interact with the catalytic subunit of the enzymes. PS acts as a cofactor of protein kinases through the interaction between the fatty acid chains of PS with the hydrophobic sites of the enzyme. PE, PC affect the activity of the respiratory chain elements, the activity of cytochrome oxidase.

CL is a marker lipid for mitochondria and plays an important role in the functioning of electron-transfer systems. FI is involved in the formation of ATP. PC, PS, FI are involved in the conformation of cytochrome P450 and its active participation in microsomal oxidation. The

functions of lipids in membranes can be combined into 4 main types: 1) barrier; 2) participation in the implementation of the action of hormones, mediators; 3) participation in membrane transport; 4) influence on the activity of enzymes.

Thus, an increase in the intensity of LPO, an increase in the activation of lysosomal enzymes, a violation of the activity of phospholipid biosynthesis enzymes leads to a decrease in the amount of total phospholipids - about inhibition of phospholipid synthesis. A decrease in the activity of the antioxidant enzyme SOD indicates an increase in the LPO process, depletion of the antioxidant system, a decrease in the amount of antioxidants in the organ. It is known that SOD deactivates acid radicals, being considered their "cleaner". These changes lead to deformation of the phospholipid bilayer of cell membranes and washing out of cytoplasmic enzymes into the blood.

Conclusion. The activity of ALT and AST in the blood serum of experimental animals increased by 2.4 - 2.6 times. Thus, with toxic heliotropin hepatitis, the following changes occurred: a change in their permeability, a violation of the microsomal and mitochondrial oxidation pathways, a hypoxic state, a violation of the integrity and an increase in the permeability of cytoplasmic, as well as lysosomal membranes, a decrease in the activity of enzymes of the antioxidant system (AOS), a decrease in the concentration of antioxidants, which leads to a violation of their metabolism and the development of an immunodeficiency state. These changes require the introduction of antioxidants (alpha-tocopherol, ascorbic acid) and a membrane regenerator - liposomes, isolated from healthy organs, capable of transferring medicinal substances contained in them, and after transferring the drugs included in them, to integrate into the membranes of the affected organs and enhance their regeneration.

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